

FAULT CURRENT REDUCTION IN DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM USING FUZZY BASED ACTIVE SFCL

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ABSTRACT

In the modern power system, as the utilization of electric power is very wide, there is a frequent occurring of any fault or disturbance in power system. It causes a high short circuit current. Due to this fault, high currents occurs results to large mechanical forces, these forces cause overheating of the equipment. If the large size equipment are used in power system then they need a large protection scheme for severe fault conditions. Generally, the maintenance of electrical power system reliability is more important. But the elimination of fault is not possible in power systems. So the only alternate solution is to minimize the fault currents. For this the Super Conducting Fault Current Limiter using fuzzy logic technique is the best electric equipment which is used for reducing the severe fault current levels. In this paper, we simulated the unsymmetrical and symmetrical faults with fuzzy based superconducting fault current limiter. In our analysis it is proved that, fuzzy logic based super conducting fault current limiter reduces fault current quickly to a lower value.

Index Terms: Distribution Generation (DG), Distribution System, Short-Circuit Current, SFCL, Fuzzy Logic.

INTRODUCTION

In the present scenario, power quality and power supply are the main problems in power system. The distributed generation (DG) system has got lot of importance because of the limitation of conventional power generation [1]-[3]. The main advantage of DG system is it reduces transmission cost. It has high quality and provide power to loads to maintain continuous supply. Voltage sags and swells are also one of the most regular energy top quality disruptions in power systems. It is necessary to examine voltage sags and swells due to consumer's utilization of power at different times. Due to faults also the voltage sags and